

ECONOMIC EVALUATION OF CROP LOAN WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO GRAPES GROWERS IN NASHIK DISTRICT.

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Abstract

The present study, titled "Economic Evaluation of Crop Loan with Special Reference to Grapes Growers in Nashik District," aims to assess the utilization patterns, repayment behavior, and credit-related challenges faced by grape farmers. Conducted in the Niphad and Chandwad tehsils of Nashik, Maharashtra, a region known as the "Grape Capital of India," the research is based on primary data collected from 50 randomly selected grape growers through structured interviews. The study reveals that although institutional credit is available, farmers often face issues such as delayed loan disbursement, lengthy documentation, collateral requirements, and insufficient loan amounts. As a result, many resort to borrowing from moneylenders, despite high-interest rates. A significant proportion of the respondents are small and marginal farmers who use crop loans primarily for agricultural purposes; however, loan diversion to non-agricultural uses and high default rates were observed. Defaulting was largely due to low produce prices, irregular income, and expectations of debt waivers. The study highlights the importance of improving financial literacy, streamlining loan procedures, encouraging timely repayment, and promoting climate-resilient practices. Addressing these challenges can enhance the effectiveness of agricultural credit systems and contribute to the long-term sustainability and economic stability of grape growers in the region.

Keywords- Crop Loan, grape farmers, interest rates, sustainability and economic stability.

Introduction:

Agriculture remains the backbone of India's economy, with grapes emerging as a key commercial fruit crop in states like Maharashtra. However, grapes growers face numerous challenges, including erratic weather, high input costs, pest issues, market fluctuations, and limited credit access. India's agricultural credit system comprises both institutional and non-institutional sources, with schemes like the Kisan Credit Card and Interest Subvention Scheme aiming to improve financial access. Despite these efforts, grapes, particularly smallholders in districts like Nashik, struggle due to inadequate infrastructure, complex procedures, and mounting loan defaults. Nashik, a leading grape producing district, is marked by small landholdings, uneven irrigation, and frequent climate shocks, necessitating timely and affordable credit. Strengthening loan disbursement systems, improving financial literacy, and expanding crop insurance and market support are essential to ensuring sustainability, resilience, and economic growth for grape growers in the region.

Objectives

- 1) To study socio-economic characteristics of selected grapes growers.
- 2) To evaluate the repayment schedule adopted by grapes growers.
- 3) To identify the constraints for borrowing and repayment of loan by selected grapes growers.

Methodology:

This section will focus on the source of data, period of the data, methods adopted to achieve the objectives.

Source of data: In this research, data was sourced from both primary means. Primary data was collected directly from grape growers through schedules and interviews.

Analytical Tools:

Variables to study socio-economic:

Family size 2) Family income 3) Level of education 4) Age 5) Sex 6) Category 7) Operational land holdings 8) Social Participation 9) Mass media access 10) Material possession 11) Occupation 12) Farming experience 13) Perception on climate change 14) Knowledge on mitigation and adaption practices in agriculture
(The simple tabular analysis was made to explain the socio-economic characteristics of selected grapes growers.)

Repayment plan

The repayment schedule data from grapes growers was analysed and compared with the standard repayment schedule of the financing agency.

Constraints for borrowing and repayment of loan by selected grapes growers.

Constraints for borrowing and repayment of loans identified and achieved by percentage and averages.

Results and Discussion**Socio-economic characteristics of selected grapes growers in Nashik District**

Socio-economic Characteristics is a broad concept that includes income, education, occupation, and subjective perceptions of social Characteristics and social class. It is a combined measurement of the economic and social position of an individual or group in relation to others in the society.

Demographic characteristics of selected loan borrowers grapes growers in Nashik District.

The majority of grape growers are in the age group of 31–50 years, with medium-sized families. Most are educated up to the 8th–12th standard, and all respondents are male. The sample includes farmers from diverse caste groups, with a higher share from OBC and Open categories.

Farming experience, Occupation, Social participation, and Land holding of Loan borrowers' grapes growers in Nashik District.

Table 1. Age, Family size, Education level, Sex and Caste of Loan borrower grapes growers in Nashik District.

Sr. No.	Variables	Category	No of Farmers	Per cent Share
1	Age (In years)	Below 20	0	0.00
		21-30	2	4.00
		31-40	13	26.00
		41-50	19	38.00

		51-60	11	22.00
		61 and above	5	10.20
2	Family	Small (Up to 3)	4	8.00
		Medium (4-6)	31	62.00
		Large (Above 6)	15	30.00
3	Education	Illiterate	4	8.00
		1-7 Standards	14	28.00
		8-12 Standards	24	48.00
		Graduate Level	8	16.00
4	Sex	Male	100	100.0
		Female	0	0.00
5	Caste	OPEN	15	30.00
		OBC	16	32.00
		SC/ST	9	18.00
		VJNT	10	20.00

Table 2 Farming experience, Occupation, Social participation, and Land holding of Loan borrowers' grapes growers in Nashik District.

Sr. No.	Variables	Category	No of growers	Per cent Share
1	Farming Experience (In years)	01-20	24	48.00
		21-40	18	36.00
		41-60	8	16.00
2	Occupation	Agriculture	43	86.00
		Agriculture and Service	5	10.00
		Agriculture and Business	2	4.00
3	Social Participation	Regularly	16	32.00
		Occasionally	27	54.00
		No Participation	7	14.00
4	Land Holding	Marginal (Up to 2.5 Acre)	22	44.00
		Small (2.5 to 5 Acre)	24	48.00
		Medium (5 to 10 Acre)	4	8.00

Most grape growers have 1–20 years of farming experience and are primarily engaged in agriculture. A majority participate socially on an occasional basis. In terms of landholding, most farmers are marginal or small landholders, highlighting the dominance of small-scale farming in

the study area.

Material possession of Loan borrowers' grapes growers in Nashik District

Table 3 Material possession of loan borrowers' grapes growers in Nashik district

Sr. No.	Variables	Category	No of growers	Per cent Share
1	Mechanical Assets	Tractor	39	78.00
		Sprinkler Sets	2	4.00
		Drippers Set	50	100.00
		Other Farm Equipment	29	58.00
2	Livestock	Goat	3	11.67
		Cow	46	33.33
		Buffalo	20	40.00
		Bullock Pair	2	12.00
3	Mass Media	Feature Phone	16	26.67
		Smart Phone	32	53.33
		Newspaper	5	8.33
		Television	56	93.33

The data reveals that a majority of grape growers possess essential mechanical assets, especially other farm equipment (96.67%) and sprinkler sets (63.33%). Livestock ownership is moderate, with cows

(33.33%) and buffaloes (40%) being the most common. In terms of mass media access, smartphones (53.33%) and televisions (93.33%) are widely used, indicating good access to information and communication

tools. Overall, farmers show reasonable asset ownership, which supports grape cultivation and access to agricultural updates.

Annual income of Loan borrowers' grapes growers in Nashik District

Table 4 . Annual income of Loan borrowers' grapes growers in Nashik District

Sr. No.	Category (Rs.)	No. of Farmers	Per cent Share	Average Income (Rs.)
1	51000-100000	2	4	75,500
2	100000-150000	6	12	1,25,000
3	Above 150000	42	84	1,75,000
Total		50	100	

The majority of grape growers (84%) earn above ₹1,50,000 annually, with an average income of ₹1,75,000, indicating a relatively high-income level among the sample. Only a small portion falls in the lower income brackets.

4. Knowledge about mitigation and adaption practices to the Loan Borrowers Farmers in Nashik District

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Table 5. Knowledge about mitigation and adaption practices to the Loan borrowers grapes growers in Nashik district.

Sr. No.	Category	No. of Farmers	Percentage share
1	Knows about mitigation practices	40	80.00
2	Does not know about mitigation	10	20.00
3	Implemented mitigation practices	30	60.00
4	Did not implement mitigation	30	60.00
5	Knows about adaptation practices	42	84.00
6	Does not know about adaptation	8	16.00
7	Implemented adaptation practices	30	60.00
8	Did not implement adaptation	17	34.00

A majority of grape-growing loan borrowers in Nashik are aware of both mitigation (80.00%) and adaptation (84.00%) practices. However, only 60.00% have implemented these measures, indicating a gap between

knowledge and actual practice. This highlights the need for better support and incentives to promote the adoption of climate-resilient strategies.

Perception on climate change of Loan borrowers' grapes growers in Nashik District.

Table 6 Perception on climate change of Loan borrowers' grapes growers in Nashik District.

Sr. No.	Particular	Response option	No. of Farmers	Percentage share
1	Awareness of climate change	Very aware	40	80.00
		Somewhat aware	5	10.00
		Not aware	5	10.00
2	Belief in Human- Caused Climate Change	Human activities	38	76.00
		Natural processes	5	10.00
		Both	5	1.00
		Unsure	2	0.4
3	Concern about climate change	Agree	42	84.00
		Neutral	5	10.00
		Disagree	3	6.00
4	Made Lifestyle Changes Due to Climate Change	Yes	27	54.00
		No	23	46.00
5	Biggest Barriers to Taking Climate Action	Lack of information	18	36.00
		Cost	10	20.00
		Inconvenience	10	20.00
		Doubts about effectiveness	8	16.00
		Other	4	8.00

Most grape growers in Nashik are highly aware (80.00%) and concerned (84.00%) about climate change, with many attributing it to human activities. However, only 54.00% have made lifestyle changes in response. Key barriers to climate action include lack of information, cost,

and doubts about effectiveness, indicating the need for targeted awareness programs and support to overcome these challenges.

4.2.1 Repayment schedule adopted by Loan borrowers in Nashik District.

Table 7 Repayment schedule adopted by Loan borrowers in Nashik District.

Sr. No.	Loan Scheme	Sub Category	Number of borrower growers	Regular Repayment (In No)	Defaulter	Per cent	Share
1	Institutional Loans	Bank	42	16	26	100	
2	Non institutional	Moneylender	8	8	0	0	
	Total		50	24	26	100	

There are 26 grapes growers who are defaulters of institutional loans, accounting for 52% of the total borrowers.

Out of 50 grape growers, 26 (52%) are loan defaulters, all from institutional sources, making up 52.00% of total institutional borrowers. In contrast, all moneylender borrowers repaid their loans regularly,

indicating stricter or more immediate repayment enforcement in non-institutional lending.

4.2.2 Repayment behaviour of Loan borrowers' grapes growers in Nashik District

Table 8 Repayment behaviour of Loan borrowers' grapes growers in Nashik District.

Sr. No.	Variables	Categories	No. of growers	Percent	Share
1	Extent of Repayment	Fully Repaid	17	34.00	
		Partly Repaid	7	14.00	
		Fully Not Repaid	26	52.00	
		Total	50	100.0	
2	Reasons For the Full Repayment	To Take Another Loan	0	0.00	
		To Maintain Credibility	2	11.76	
		Proper Supervision by the sources	15	88.23	
		Total	17	100.0	
3	Reasons For the Partial Repayment of Loan	Insufficient Income	5	71.42	
		Crop Failures	2	28.57	
		Family Problems and Expenses on Health and Education of Children	0	0.00	
		Total	7	100.0	
4	Reasons For the Fully Not Repayment of Loan	Expecting Debt Waiver and Debt Reliefs by Government	21	80.76	
		Less of Agricultural Income	2	7.69	
		Low Price for or Agricultural Produce	3	11.53	
		Total	26	100.0	

Among grape growers, 52% fully defaulted on loan repayment, mainly due to expectations of government debt waivers (80.76%). Only 34% fully repaid, largely due to proper supervision by loan sources. Partial repayment (14%) was mostly due to insufficient income and crop failure.

This highlights the need for better credit monitoring and support systems to improve repayment rates.

4.3. Constraints in borrowing and repayment of loans by selected grapes growers.

Table 9 Constraints faced by grapes growers in borrowing bank loans.

Sr. No	Constraints	No of growers	Percent	Rank
1	Lengthy Documentation and Formalities	36	85.00	I
2	Insufficient loan amounts	30	71.00	II
3	Lack of knowledge about loan availing procedure	19	45.00	III
4	Credit Score Issues	15	35.00	V
5	Behaviors of bank officials are not Cooperative	11	26.00	VI

The main constraints faced by grape growers in borrowing bank loans include lengthy documentation (85.00%) and insufficient loan amounts (71.00%). Issues like credit scores, lack of knowledge, and non-

cooperative bank officials also hinder access, highlighting the need for simplified procedures and improved growers bank interactions.

Table 10 Constraints faced by grapes growers in Repayment of bank loans.

Sr. No	Constraints	No of growers	Per cent	Rank
1	Low price of produce	39	92.00	I
2	Low or irregular income	35	83.00	II
3	Crop Failure Due to Weather Conditions	30	71.00	III
4	Expecting Debt Waiver and Debt Relief by the Government	18	42.00	IV
5	Sudden emergencies	6	14.00	V

The major constraints in bank loan repayment among grape growers are the low price of produce (92.00%), irregular income (83.00%), and crop failure due to weather (71.00%). Expectations of debt waivers and

sudden emergencies also impact repayment, reflecting the vulnerability of farmers to market and climatic risks.

Table 11 Constraints faced by grapes growers in borrowing loans from moneylenders.

Sr. No	Constraints	No of growers	Per cent	Rank
1	Demand for Collateral	7	87.50	I
2	High Interest Rates	5	65.50	II
3	No Legal Protection	4	50.00	III
4	Lack of Transparency	3	37.50	IV

Grape growers relying on non-institutional loans face key constraints such as demand for collateral (87.5%), high interest rates (65.5%), and

lack of legal protection (50%). These issues highlight the risks and financial stress associated with borrowing from moneylenders.

Table 12 Constraints faced by grapes growers in repayment loan from moneylenders.

Sr. No	Constraints	No of growers	Per cent	Rank
1	High Interest Burden	6	75.00	I
2	Lack of Record or Proof	5	62.50	II
3	No Flexibility in Repayment	3	37.00	III
4	Irregular and Seasonal Income	2	25.00	IV

Grape growers face major challenges in repaying moneylender loans, primarily due to the high interest burden (75%) and lack of proper records (62.5%). Limited repayment flexibility and irregular income further add to their difficulties, emphasizing the need for more regulated and farmer-friendly credit options.

5. Conclusion

The economic evaluation of crop loans among grape growers in Nashik district reveals that while institutional credit plays a crucial role in supporting agriculture, its effectiveness is hindered by procedural barriers and inconsistent repayment. A large number of growers default due to factors like low income, crop failures, and market instability. Non-institutional sources, though more accessible, come with higher risks. To improve credit outcomes, there is a need for policy reforms focused on timely disbursement, simplified procedures, awareness programs, and stronger support systems tailored to the unique needs of small and marginal grape growers.

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